

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-72-IG-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	5	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 72
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/16/2022 10:37:35 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 4:54:33 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	4.111	20697	1.45	3242
2	4.311	689137	48.18	109938
3	4.718	697531	48.77	101837
4	5.059	23012	1.61	2750

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-61-IG-5% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221116
Vial:	6	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 61
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/16/2022 11:45:29 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 4:58:20 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	4.101	50593	2.07	9275
2	4.290	2350284	96.24	384923
3	4.704	20476	0.84	3878
4	5.037	20652	0.85	3823